

Status of the MICADO PSF Reconstruction Tool and Validation with ERIS@VLT

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ABSTRACT

The Multi-AO Imaging Camera for Deep Observations (MICADO) will be the first-light imager of ESO Extremely Large Telescope. With first light expected by the end of 2030, interest is growing in preparing for the exploitation of its unique capabilities. PSF reconstruction (PSF-R) will be a key service provided by the MICADO consortium to meet performance requirements in most science cases, and especially for the extra-galactic domain, with targets usually selected at high galactic latitudes, lacking bright stars. MICADO PSF-R will be carried out in post-processing, using a telemetry-only approach to generate template PSFs for each observation, independent of the science data. It will rely on AO telemetry recorded synchronously with the science exposures, as well as atmospheric parameters, including wind profiles. For the initial phase of operations - limited to SCAO - PSF-R will deliver both on-axis and off-axis PSFs through a state-of-the-art tomographic approach. In this presentation, we will present the status of the project and discuss the latest results from an observing campaign begun in 2023 using ERIS at the VLT. The aim is to target a bright, sparse asterism of three stars under various conditions (e.g., filters, airmass), to build a reference dataset covering a wide parameter space. These data are being used to

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fine-tune the PSF-R method for SCAO with MICADO. Analysis of 2023 data under good seeing (< 1 arcsec) at $2.2\ \mu\text{m}$ shows $\sim 10\%$ accuracy in Strehl ratio and FWHM, even at 16 arcsec off-axis distance. The angle between wind vectors and off-axis directions appears to be a major source of uncertainty. Additional datasets from 2024–2025 are under analysis, and preliminary results will be presented. Finally, the impact of PSF-R precision on key science cases is being evaluated and will be discussed, assessing the ELT expectations.

Keywords: PSF Reconstruction, SCAO, NIR-imaging, MICADO, ELT

1. INTRODUCTION

The Extremely Large Telescope (ELT) is rapidly becoming a reality. By 2029, the telescope will be operative, equipped with the Multi-AO Imaging Camera for Deep Observations (MICADO, [3]). This first-light instrument incorporates a single-conjugated AO (SCAO) system enabling imaging at an unprecedented spatial resolution and sensitivity for a near-infrared, ground-based facility (its capabilities will be further extended when the Multiconjugate adaptive Optics Relay For ELT Observations - MORFEO, [1] - becomes operational). Given the relatively high temporal and spatial variability of the PSF in such an AO-assisted instrument, accurately characterising the PSF plays a crucial role for exploiting the full scientific potential of the instrument: MICADO will be one of the first ESO instruments that, by design, will provide the final user a PSF reconstruction (PSF-R) service. A work package of the MICADO consortium is dedicated to its development ([13, 5]). Specifically, the MICADO PSF-R algorithm [18] rely on a telemetry-only philosophy, enabling the derivation of the on-axis SCAO PSF without any information coming from the scientific images. This means that templates PSFs can be derived even when no suitable point sources are present in the scientific field of view (FoV), a common situation in typical extragalactic fields, for example. The MICADO PSF-R algorithm was proven to work once applied to real SCAO on-axis, SOUL+LUCI@LBT observations. A precision of the order of 2 – 5% in both Strehl Ratio (SR) and full-width at half maximum (FWHM) has been achieved in the reconstruction of the on-axis PSF, also highlighting the versatility of the method [14]. In a recent development, [19] presented an extension of the MICADO PSF-R method to include SCAO off-axis cases. Through a temporal tomography, the algorithm aims to reliably reconstruct, in post-processing, the SCAO off-axis PSFs starting from input turbulence and wind profiles. The method is being tested in both end-to-end simulations (e.g. [19]) and with real data ([16, 15]). In particular, data collected so far seems to indicate that winds play a crucial role for the proposed method, especially for ground-based, AO-assisted, 40m-class telescopes. We are currently relying on wind predictions by [8], underlying the importance of considering programs like the FATE project ([9]) also for the ELT.

Finally, the scientific evaluation of the reconstructed PSFs is currently being performed. This has a significant impact on identifying science-driven constraints for MICADO PSF-R. Using simulated MICADO SCAO off-axis PSFs, we quantify the impact of our PSF-R on a selected, idealised scientific case: the morphology of compact star-forming regions (clumps) in high-redshift galaxies. This is a key science goal of MICADO, because at $z=2$, $\sim 60\%$ of galaxies appear to be hosting compact star-forming regions [12]. However, to grasp their nature, investigations to sub-kpc scales are needed [17]. Presently, this is possible only by exploiting strong gravitational lensing, even with facilities such as the James Webb Space Telescope (see e.g. [10] and [2]). With MICADO, instead, it will be possible to overcome current limitations.

For completeness, in Figure 1 we qualitatively show the advantage of using MICADO for the proposed science case. Real Hubble Space Telescope observations of NGC1705 have been used (copied three times, each rotated by a different angle) to generate a mock compact star-forming region hosting 3 main sub-clumps. The resulting star-forming region has a size of $R_{\text{eff}} = 285$ pc and we place it at redshift $z=2.31$. The model image used, at full resolution, is shown in the left panel of Figure 1, its size highlighted with an azure circle. The central panel clearly shows that, even without gravitational lensing, MICADO allows the characterisation of the sub-clumps. In comparison, this is not achievable with the James Webb Space Telescope (right panel). In both the middle and right panels, the size of the associated PSF is represented by a white circle in the bottom-left corner.

2. DATA

We extend the data sample presented in [16] and [15], including recent observations acquired in the context of an ESO technical time request (TTR) dedicated to obtaining ERIS@VLT observations specifically devised for PFS-R. As with the previous dataset, the new data consists of ERIS@VLT[4] SCAO observations of a bright asterism, the same as [16]. Three bright stars are present in the observed FoV, one of them has been used as the AO reference star (i.e. has been observed on-axis) while the other 2 have a radial distance of $7''$ and $16''$ respectively. Magnitudes are in the range $H=9-9.5$ VEGAmag, and the new observations (acquired in March 2024) have been performed in different wavelength ranges. Three narrowband filters have been used: Pa-b ($\lambda_c = 1.282\ \mu\text{m}$), Fe-II ($\lambda_c = 1.644\ \mu\text{m}$) and K-peak ($\lambda_c = 2.198\ \mu\text{m}$). We analysed 3 streams of 252s of continuous observations

Figure 1. Given its exceptional spatial resolution and sensitivity, MICADO is able to characterise the sub-clumps of an imaginary $z=2$ compact star-forming region of size $R_{\text{eff}} = 285$ pc (azure circle in all panels). While MICADO can spatially resolve the sub-clumps, the James Webb Space Telescope have a PSF FWHM (white circles in the bottom-left corner of the rightmost panel) comparable with the azure circle. The central panel assumes a k-band, SCAO PSF $30''$ off-axis.

subdivided into frames of 0.9s each. As for the ERIS TTR dataset presented in [16], the data is accompanied by the associated AO telemetry, recorded simultaneously to the scientific observations with a frequency of 1KHz. Following [16], for each 2024 ERIS TTR dataset, MASS/DIMM turbulence profile was adopted (obtained from the ESO archive) along with specific wind predictions for Paranal ([8]). Even though different wavelength ranges have been sampled, for the off-axis SCAO PSF-R, we used the same recipe of [16]. Specifically, at the time, ERIS Fe-II narrowband observations have been used to calibrate the PSF-R method: both the wavelength- and temporal- invariance of the method have been tested. In addition to ERIS data, the [16] and [15] sample includes the reconstruction of simulated MICADO@ELT SCAO off-axis PSFs ([19]) and SOUL+LUCI on-axis ones ([14]). All are included in the present discussion.

3. DISCUSSION

Figure 2. Performance of MICADO SCAO PSF-R among different cases. Both the analysis of real observations and end-to-end simulations are considered. A classic PSF metric is shown, SR absolute values are reported in the upper row, FWHM in the middle row, and EE_{CORE} values are shown in the bottom row. Black symbols indicate reference values (different symbols have been used for different wavelengths), while red crosses indicate the ones measured on reconstructed PSFs.

The main result of the current investigation is reported in Figure 2. The performance of our PSF-R SCAO method is quantified through a classical PSF metric described by SR (upper row), FWHM (middle row), and encircled energy in the PSF core (EE_{CORE} , bottom row). Absolute observed (reference) values are shown in black; different symbols have been used to discriminate between different wavelength ranges. Reconstructed values are shown, instead, as red crosses. Vertical dotted lines subdivide the sample into four blocks, differentiating on- from off-axis sources and real observations from simulated ones. The leftmost block shows the result associated with the on-axis PSF-R of real SCAO observation obtained with both SOUL+LUCI@LBT and ERIS@VLT (in this case, on different dates). It can be noted that our PSF-R method produced consistent results with a precision of the order of 5 – 10% in all the considered parameters. These results corroborate what was obtained from simulated SCAO on-axis observations (second block from left, see [16] for details). As concerns SCAO off-axis PSF-R performance, in the case of real observations, a heterogeneous sample is shown in Figure 2. As mentioned, given the selected asterism, 2 points are associated with each set, one refers to the 7" off-axis source, the other to the 16" one. The newly added ERIS TTR of March 2024 added 6 points to the real off-axis block. It can be noticed that the atmospheric conditions, in this case, were worse than those of April 2023 set: the observed SR at $1.65\mu\text{m}$ is $\sim 30\%$ less. Nonetheless, the performance of the method is still consistent. This is especially true if the wavelength dependence of the isoplanatic patch is taken into consideration. We underline that, for the reconstruction of ERIS 2024 TTR, we used the same recipe tuned for ERIS 2023 TTR data. This demonstrates the flexibility and robustness of the method. In the rightmost block of Figure 2, we report the results for SCAO off-axis simulated MICADO observations. The observed SR values in this case are around 10% because the target source was placed at 30" from the AO reference star. With simulated data, the precision reached 30" off-axis, at $2.2\mu\text{m}$, is at the level of 5%. For the real ERIS sources, with an off-axis distance of 16", at $1.65\mu\text{m}$, the error in SR is $\sim 20\%$. This somewhat worse performance for real data may be caused by the loss of information due to specific wind orientations. Further analysis is being performed.

The encouraging results we are obtaining with our PSF-R method, especially for SCAO off-axis reconstruction, prompted the evaluation of using the reconstructed PSFs on MICADO scientific cases. The scientific evaluation of the MICADO PSF-R, as mentioned, is particularly relevant at this stage because it will not only help identify science-driven constraints for the MICADO PSF-R. It will also corroborate the early scientific exploitation of the instrument. The selected science case is the characterisation, in terms of size and luminosity, of clumps in $z=2$, non-lensed galaxies. The present analysis is the focus of a dedicated work (Simioni et al., submitted), and we will discuss here just some relevant aspects, aiming at demonstrating that the achieved precision in reconstructing the SCAO off-axis PSF enables the exploitation of MICADO in this specific science case. In this exercise, we started from an idealised model of a typical $z=2$ galaxy, hosting clumps of different sizes and magnitudes. We used GALFIT [11] to generate the input model. The parameter space has been determined using, as a reference, the samples from [10] and [2], both relying on observations of strongly lensed systems, with gravitational magnifications up to a factor 80 for the smallest (and faintest) clumps. Using SimCADO ([7, 6]) we were able to simulate MICADO observation. To be conservative, we focused on simulating K-band observations of 3hr total exposure time using a SCAO, 30" off-axis PSF. The used MICADO PSF has been produced in the context of the instrument final design review in 2021.

Using again GALFIT, we performed two distinct measures on the resulting simulated image. First, we perform a control measure, giving as input to GALFIT the reference PSF. This allows us to take into account any bias introduced by the measuring process itself. In this way, we also observed that, even knowing the PSF with extreme accuracy, clumps with sizes less than 2 mas (0.5 MICADO pixel) cannot be characterised. The actual measure has been performed, providing GALFIT with the reconstructed PSF. The resulting comparison between control and actual measurements is shown in Figure 3, for size and magnitude determination on the left and right panel, respectively. In both cases, the absolute difference is shown, using colours to highlight the dependence on the non-considered parameter in both cases. Concerning the size, the left panel of Figure 3 shows that the use of the reconstructed PSF introduces an error of 20% – 30%, even for the most compact ones, at around 20 pc. The error, in the case of magnitude, is of the order of 0.1 – 0.2 mag.

4. CONCLUSION

MICADO will be one of the first ESO instruments that integrates PSF-R into the design. The final users will be provided with template PSFs corroborating their observations: the MICADO PSF-R will be included in the instrument pipeline (developed in the ESO EDPS framework). In the case of MICADO, a telemetry-only approach is adopted, allowing the derivation of reconstructed PSFs without relying on information coming from the scientific field of view. The MICADO PSF-R will, instead, rely on AO telemetry, atmospheric condition monitoring and precise calibrations.

Figure 3. Absolute error introduced in size (left panel) and luminosity (right panel, rest-frame UV magnitude is used) characterisation of mock clump population if a reconstructed MICADO PSF is used, instead of the nominal one. Dotted curves in the left panels represent curves of constant relative error. For $R \lesssim 2$ mas (0.5 MICADO px) size determination is not possible, even with a perfect knowledge of the PSF. The resulting avoidance region is highlighted, in the left panel, by the grey-shaded area.

The proposed method ([18, 19]) has been validated on real SCAO on-axis observations [14]. The reconstruction of SCAO off-axis PSFs is currently being tested, exploiting a dedicated ESO TTR. In this context, different ERIS observations are being collected targeting bright asterisms in different atmospheric and instrumental conditions. As a result, the parameter space sample is growing. Analysis of the collected data is ongoing, and preliminary results are encouraging. The analysis of the ERIS 2023 TTR suggests that our PSF-R method can reach a precision of the order of 10% – 20% in SR, FWHM and encircled energy, even for off-axis distances up to half the isoplanatic angle ($\sim 16''$ at $1.65 \mu\text{m}$, [15]). Furthermore, the consistency of the results among distinct datasets confirms the robustness and flexibility of the method, even when different wavelengths are considered, as in the case of ERIS 2024 TTR.

Finally, an effort towards the scientific evaluation of MICADO PSF-R has been presented. Specifically, we focused on the characterisation of compact star-forming regions in $z = 2$ galaxies. Using reconstructed PSF, MICADO will be able to characterise clumps up to sizes of 20 – 30 pc in non-lensed $z = 2$ galaxies. These results support an effective, early exploitation of the MICADO instrument.

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